

ExAMPLER Exascale ABMSS Roadmap

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Exascale Definition:

“64 bit double precision high performance LINPACK – HPLin-
pack to achieve 10^{18} floating point operations per second (FLOPS).”

NOTE: double precision floating point benchmarks are required to break
the official exaFLOP mark. [Jac24], [Pet+18], [DL11]

Deliverable: Report on a roadmap for exascale computing to support
the empirical agent-based modelling community (including an executive
summary and glossary), uploaded to Zenodo.

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Abstract

Over a period of 18 months, the ExAMPLER¹ project has worked with the agent-based modelling and social simulation (ABMSS) community to draft a roadmap towards the use of exascale computing. The results of a systematic literature review (SLR) are presented, leading to the conclusion that the use of high performance computing (HPC) is under-represented in this area compared to other scientific disciplines. The move from desktop models to exascale models requires a revolution in the libraries, frameworks and working practices currently being employed in order to take advantage of the unprecedented level of parallelism offered at exascale. In addition to this, we present our research from running workshops designed to provide a vision of how exascale can be a benefit to ABMSS research. The science case for why exascale is essential to future ABMSS research is made, demonstrating how more compute intensive models with increased numbers of agents and interactions can produce vastly different results. In addition to this, the power of exascale computing makes it possible to perform sensitivity analysis at a scale not possible before. The roadmap presented here is built from the responses of the ABMSS community during these workshop discussions.

1 Introduction

The agent based modelling for social simulation roadmap presented here is the result of 18 months of work by the UKRI funded ExAMPLER project. Its scope is to determine the readiness of ABMSS to step up to the level of exascale class computing and to set out the steps needed to achieve this. Between June 2023 and November 2024, a number of workshops were run to elicit responses from the ABMSS community, to determine their visions for the future and to begin drafting this roadmap. These workshops are discussed in the following section 1.1. In addition to this, a systematic literature review (SLR) has been conducted to identify any prior uses of High Performance Computing (HPC) and agent-based modelling and the results of this exercise are presented in section 1.6. Finally, in the background section 4, the literature leading up to the procurement phases of the U.S. Exascale computers is reviewed, along with the European research.

The current situation at the time of writing (May 2024) is that the first Exascale computer, “Frontier”, is installed and working at Oak Ridge National Laboratories (ORNL). This is to be followed shortly by “Aurora” at the Argonne National Labs (ANL) and “El Capitan” at the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratories (LLNL). The purchase of a U.K. National Exascale computer is scheduled for late 2024, destined to replace ARCHER2 at EPCC in Edinburgh. There exist good reasons

¹ExAMPLER: Exascale Agent-based Modelling for Policy Evaluation in Real-time

to believe that a plan for ABMSS is required. Firstly, the main users of the current generation of Petascale HPC would appear to exclude most agent-based modelling and social science. This is born out in the systematic literature review and the review of the Exascale Project “Proxy apps” in section 4.3. Secondly, by analysing the architecture of a deployed and working Exascale computer and contrasting this with the current state of the art in agent-based modelling software, there are concerns raised about how to step up to Exascale. Taking a Frontier compute node as an example, this comprises four Radeon Instinct MI250X GPUs and one AMD EPYC 7453 Trento CPU. Exascale computers achieve their speed through GPU acceleration, so agent-based modelling software needs to be adapted to run on the new architectures. Section 5.2 contains a review of agent based modelling frameworks and whether they are GPU accelerated. The overarching question which came out of the International Exascale Software Project (IESP) roadmap [DBa11] is one of “Evolution or Revolution?”. Can existing software be adapted, or is it a case of throwing it away and starting with something new? This was the focus of the roadmap workshop held at Glasgow University in April 2024.

1.1 Visioning Workshops, Roadmap Workshops and Other Events

The following are events attended during the course of the ExAMPLER project, beginning with the workshops.

Workshop Events Organised by ExAMPLER:

- 4-8 September 2023, Visioning Workshop, Social Simulation Conference (SSC23), Glasgow University, “*Visions for exascale computing support for empirical ABSS*”
- 8-9 November 2023, London Visioning Workshop, UCL, “*Identifying the Crucial Challenges for ABMSS at Exascale*”
- 29-30 April 2024, Glasgow Roadmap Workshop, Glasgow University, “*Roadmap to Agent-Based Modelling at Exascale*”
- 26 June 2024, iEMSs Roadmap Workshop, Michigan, workshop over Zoom, “*A roadmap to exascale computing in coupled social-environmental modelling of complex systems*”
- 16 September 2024, Roadmap Workshop, Social Simulation Conference (SSC24), Krakow, Poland, “*A roadmap to exascale agent-based modelling*”
- November 2024, Final Workshop, UCL? TBA

Papers/Abstracts/Conferences:

- SSC 2023, Glasgow University, September 2023, (Poster presentation [Pol+23a])
- RofASSS 2023 article [Pol+23b]
- GIScience 2023, paper [Hep+23]
- ExCALIBUR at CIUK 2023, conference talk [HSR23]
- NHR Conference, Berlin, September 2023, invited talk: [Pol23]
- Exposome-NL Conference, Utrecht, November 2023, Keynote talk: [PH23]
- Computing Insight UK (CIUK), Manchester, December 2023, conference talk: [HSR23]
- AAG 2024, Honolulu, April 2024, conference talk
- MABS/AAMAS 2024 (Auckland), extended abstract: [Har+24]
- HPC Days 2024, Durham University, conference talk: [Hep24]

Site visits:

- Exeter School of Mathematics, 7 Feb 2024, meeting about Gaussian Process Models

1.2 Visioning Workshop, Social Simulation Conference (SSC), Glasgow University, 4 September 2023

This was a 2 hour workshop session run at the SSC conference in Glasgow as a prelude to running the longer “visioning workshop” at UCL in November. This was an open invitation to any attendees of the SSC conference, so there was no selection of participants. The central questions that started the discussion were, “*What is exascale computing? What is its relationship to HPC? Are we doing empirical ABM differently?*”. What followed was a group model building exercise using the Visual Understanding Environment (VUE) software [Uni20] to draw a causal loop model of the potential use cases, capabilities and threats.

The outputs of this workshop are published in an AAMAS paper, “Taking Agent-Based Social Simulation to the Next Level Using Exascale Computing: Potential Use Cases, Capabilities and Threats” [Har+24].

1.3 Visioning Workshop, London, 8-9 November 2023

This was a 2 day workshop run at UCL's Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis. All the attendees from the previous Glasgow workshop were invited, plus some extra people, resulting in 13 attendees overall, not including the 5 from the ExAMPLER project hosting the event.

Introduction Presentations:

- “Introduction to the ExAMPLER project, exascale computing, ABSS and stepping up scales”, *Dr Gary Polhill (The James Hutton Institute) and Dr Richard Milton (University College London)*.

Group exercise: co-constructing a causal loop model of the potential use cases, capabilities and threats of exascale AMSS.

Talks: Experts' experiences in high-scale computing for ABSS

- Talk I: *Dr Gerry Casey (ARUP/CASA)*
- Talk II: *Dr Sarah Wise (CASA)*
- Talk III: *Professor Rob Axtell (George Mason University)* [online]
- Talk IV: *Professor Paul Richmond (University of Sheffield)*

This was followed by a panel session with the four speakers and then the second day was group work structured around, “*defining transformational use case visions in different sectors*”. The workshop concluded with presentations from the two groups and a final summary.

1.4 Roadmap Workshop, Glasgow, 29-30 April 2024

This was a 2 day workshop run at the University of Glasgow titled, “A Roadmap for Agent Based Modelling at Exascale”. Everyone from the Visioning Workshop in London was invited, along with some extras, resulting in 20 attendees. The aim of the workshop was to answer the question:

What needs to be done to achieve exascale Agent-Based Social Simulation through making the most of accelerator capabilities (parallelisation)?

Presentations from invited speakers:

- “Gaussian Process Models and Uncertainty”, *Prof. Peter Challoner (Exeter)*.
- “Research on Emulator Models”, *Dr. Louise Kimpton (Exeter)*.

- “The FACS Flu and Corona Virus Simulator and the FLEE ABM for Refugee Movement”, *Dr. Diana Suleimenova (Brunel) and Dr. Arindam Saha (UCL)*.
- “Complex Symptoms: Understanding Epidemics from the Perspective of Complexity Science”, *Dr. Sarah Wise (CASA UCL)*.

The following questions kicked off the afternoon discussion session:

“What needs to be done to achieve (parallelisation/accelerator) exascale Agent-Based Social Simulation?”

“What tools have we got at the software end that we can keep? What do we need to throw away? Or migrate? What is currently usable?”

The afternoon session started with some SLIDO questions to gauge what programming languages and frameworks people were using for ABM. Python came out top as the most used language, followed by Java, NetLogo and C++². In the next question on ABM platforms, NetLogo came top, followed by Repast and MASON. Again, we have a spread of responses that showed some people using FLAME GPU and CUDA for accelerated ABM, with a split between custom ABM programming and use of frameworks like NetLogo, Repast and MASON. Finally, the third question asked about the highest compute scale of an ABM model. This produced a very diverse spread of results, so the slide is reproduced in figure 1.

Breaking down the information in figure 1, we could group the responses by type as follows:

1. 10K, 40K, 250K, 10M, 15M, 150M (economy) agents
2. Hang Seng, an economy
3. 2 Million runs
4. Laptop, HPC (big, ish, 100s cores), Petascale, Terascale, 3e16 CPU

Point 1 shows that the absolute number of agents is how most ABM researchers are defining *big*. Point 2 is a geographical grouping, but could also be some other agglomeration of people by space or type, for example, countries, regions or other connected economies or connections. Point 3 about “2 million runs” was the only batch parallel example, which was surprising. Then, finally, point 4 is defining ABM in terms of the amount of compute used. This is potentially dangerous, as one researcher’s Terascale model running unoptimised code is another researcher’s Petascale model with more efficient programming.

²The SLIDO poll was from a total of 36 responses and 12 participants

What is the highest compute scale at which you have run an Agent-Based Model? (if not used an ABM in this case then add an asterisk to your answer...)

Wordcloud Poll 17 responses 10 participants

slido

Figure 1: Highest compute scale models questionnaire.

Defining ABM models in terms of the compute they use is a difficult path which could lead to exascale being used inefficiently. However, it does give a good theoretical framework for expressing a model in terms of compute power required in a best case implementation to make the science case for a particular problem needing exascale.

Following on from the SLIDO questions there was a more general discussion around the previous Glasgow and London visioning workshops. During this discussion, three interest group themes were identified for the following day's parallel sessions:

- Applications with SPACE (originally “Applications of...”)
- Technology
- Meta-modelling (Emulators)

The “Applications with SPACE” theme came from the ideas of agents on network graphs which could help with the extreme parallelisation required for efficient exascale models. The graph structure helps with predicting which agents can interact, as partitions can divide agents into parallel execution groups where there is guaranteed no interaction between them e.g. pure parallel. The “Technology” theme came from the idea of asking whether existing ABM technology could be modified to run on exascale, or whether a new set of tools needs to be developed? This draws on the previous questionnaires about programming

languages and whether exascale ABM is framework based or bespoke software. Finally, the “Meta-modelling (Emulators)” theme was created from the morning’s presentations on Gaussian process models, the site visit to Exeter some months earlier and the London visioning workshop, where the idea of emulator models was first thought of. The original idea behind emulator models was very simple. Basically, the exascale computer is used to build a simplified ABM model from a more computationally expensive one. This then allows researchers to run the model on laptops or regular HPC and to answer policy questions in real time. The ability to run once at exascale and then multiple times using cheaper computing gives maximum payback for the investment in exascale computing. It also side-steps the problem of having to schedule time on exascale or HPC, and offers the possibility of immediate results without having to bid for compute resources and wait for a slot to be scheduled.

Figures 3 and 4 show the causal loop diagrams produced from the end of the day 1 discussions, leading into the breakout sessions of day 2. Apparent from this discussion was the need for more theoretical work in agent based modelling relating to some of the simplifications to realism and representation that are going to be needed to run parallel models on exascale machines. The problems with ABM and parallelisation of agents, which, by the nature of the models, need to communicate with each other in large numbers of unpredictable ways was central to the discussion. The questions of whether reusable components could be used to stitch together models, or whether models use ABM frameworks, or are completely bespoke programs was also discussed. One interesting addition this time was the role of Large Language Models, which could potentially be used to write the bespoke models. The causal loop diagram in figure 4 contains the discussion around emulator models, which formed the basis for that breakout group on day 2.

Figure 2 shows the slide which was given to each breakout group for the second day. The discussion was designed to answer the question of whether we have the right tools which can be re-purposed for exascale ABM, or whether we need to develop new ones. This is crucial to the production of a roadmap for exascale ABM.

1.4.1 Applications with SPACE

- Do we have the right tools for space - NO
- Pipeline - construction of networks, scripts, temporal data, geographic boundaries - we need a community of network builders
- Synthetic populations
- Resources to build models hard - research engineers and data

Themes: Evolution or Revolution

Applications of...	Technology	Meta-modelling
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Networks (hubs?)• Spatial networks• Edge effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• GPU, data movement• Parallelisation (AWS?)• LLMs, AI?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Emulators• Policy interventions• LLMs?
Revolution / Evolution – modify old and invent new		
Cross cutting themes:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Languages?• Frameworks?• How many agents?• How do agents interact?		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Memory Limits• Time critical• What is the science case?

Figure 2: Themes for the three breakout groups the following day. NOTE: “Applications of...” became “Applications with SPACE” during the discussions.

- How to make the step up? Brunel, FABSIM3, NetLogo plugin? OpenMOLE scripting language for model exploration?
- Mixed approach, in the station people are on rasters, then going across ocean on network - use case for exascale?
- Networks are more efficient and less compute intensive. Network science very highly developed
- Memory - can we have a massive amount of memory please? The model goes faster. Is this better than having neat data structures and parallelism?
- Time Criticality - depends on application. Just in time results? Instant policy modelling - faces the pipeline problem. Data, model building blocks. Sensitivity analysis? (EASYVUQ)

1.4.2 Technology

The concrete examples in this breakout group centred around simulations of the economy with 60 million agents and firms, or simulations that run for 100,000s of virtual years.

- Fat agents, lots of agents, or both?
- Frameworks with GPU: FLAME, vertical scaling
- Frameworks with with CPU: lots of options - python (mesa, ray), java (Simudyne, Akka), C++ (repastr)

- Simulate, reinforcement learning, LLMs to make simulations or be a part of the simulation?
- Much of the conversation was around what frameworks, languages and tools already exist and how they can be re-used.
- How far can we go with CPU simulation? Is GPU needed? Simudyne example with 60M agents with Akka horizontal scaling.
- Graph computational approach - very scaleable
- Simudyne, Repast and MASON HPC versions, NetLogo toy models
- MESA +Ray Distributed ABM framework (docs.ray.io) Open source
- Importance of open source, repeatable science. Commercial products of limited use if there is even a remote possibility of them pulling support for educational use of a product in the future.

1.4.3 Meta-modelling (Emulators)

- Model in NetLogo, build metamodel/GP in R? The metamodel is called as a black box, while the model and meta model are in different languages and programs. The model is run on HPC, the emulator constructed on the desktop. The appeal of the practical and conceptual gap is clear.
- Frameworks: Scikit learn (random forests and LSTM neural networks), R packages for Gaussian processes, Python and PyTorch or TensorFlow for neural networks.
- Number of Agents: emulation doesn't see the number of agents. Mathematicians are more worried about input space dimensionality than number of agents.
- Gaussian Process doesn't scale well to large numbers of runs. Neural networks need a ton of data (Vapnik and Chervonenkis)
- Issues with space - model output is a grid over the UK - want to predict as a 'field' not a point. No standard method as yet - active area of research.
- Time criticality - no time to run simulations, but more time to run emulators. Use case of emulators as part of calibration/validation?
- Limitations: what are the limitations of emulators? Can we capture emergence? What is the input space? Need to run emulations "intelligently". Functionality of meta-modelling - what do you lose? Better than spreadsheets.

- Is there a case for rebuilding MatSim, or can we run NetLogo at exascale? Should there be a domain specific language for ABM?
- Understanding what the CPU is doing and taking advantage of that. In the Met Office they have computer scientists code equations written by fluid dynamicists.
- Opportunity to run with more agents and greater diversity. Storage and post-processing of the data is not thought about.
- Science Case: there are benefits in thinking about what we need to do to run ABMs at exascale (efficiency, tools etc.) that will be realised at lower scale. What is the information content of larger-scale simulations and how does that compare with smaller ones? (i.e. can we see the benefits in terms of information and knowledge)
- Practicality: your time to get results needs to include time waiting 'your turn' on the exascale computer. If you can access a lower scale machine more quickly, you might get your results sooner. However, if you did get priviledged access in an emergency, your need for an emulator could be reduced if the run time of the simulation on the exascale was comparable to running the emulator on a laptop.

1.4.4 Conclusions

A science case around the emergence of new effects from running bigger models at exascale still needs to be made. The technical discussions around how to run models at exascale and the theoretical discussions around running parallel simulations are pointing to high level parallelism of agent based modelling being difficult. Agents and networks was an unexpected idea to come out of the "Applications with SPACE" discussion and warrants further research. Emulators and meta-modelling appears to be an interesting area to pursue for immediacy of agent based modelling at large scale and for cost per simulation run.

1.5 Roadmap Workshop, iEMSs, Michigan, 26 June 2024

This was a 2 hour workshop run at the International Congress on Environmental Modelling and Software (iEMSs) conference in Michigan with one person running the event in Michigan and three others joining on zoom. There were five attendees in the room with the session starting with a SLIDO question and answer session, followed by a more general discussion structured around a number of research questions.

From the SLIDO questions we determined that most of the attendees worked in social science (90%), but also land use, computer science and

climate change, with no responses at all for ecology or urban studies. 75% responded that they had used agent based modelling, with Python being the main programming language (80%), although C/C++, Java and Fortran all featured with 20%. The inclusion of Fortran is interesting as it shows the language is still being used for high performance scientific applications.

The next question asked about use of ABM frameworks, with NetLogo being the most popular (80%), followed by FlameGPU (20%) and Repast (20%). However, bespoke models scored 40%, suggesting a need to support direct coding of agent based models. Given the fact that there were only 5 people attending, these figures look as though one of the participants had quite a broad, extensive knowledge of ABM, which was coming out in the C/C++, Fortran, FlameGPU and Repast scores of 20%. Nobody appeared to be using MASON, GAMA or MESA though.

For the questions on the hardware being used, this was split between laptop (80%) and HPC (80%) with desktop (60%) and local server and cloud tied on 40%. When asked about hardware limitations, memory was a clear winner with 80%, with CPU and disk space both scoring 20%. What was notable here, was that the discussion around this question cited lack of memory on the GPU as a constraining factor, which is something we hadn't considered.

Finally, for other limitations, we asked whether this was due to data (40%), technical know-how (60%), technical support staff (20%) Cloud/HPC accessibility (bureaucracy/money) (60%) or lack of AI tools (0%).

The remaining hour of discussion was built around a similar set of questions to the Glasgow Roadmap Workshop. Given the location, for the "conceptual limits" the discussion was around simulating the whole US population of 120 million. Data validation was a central topic, with the suggestion of understanding behaviour from small scale surveys and then the problems of very large scale models extrapolated from that data. How you get enough data to make a large scale model is a problem. You can also "play with the populations to affect the outcome".

In making the science case, there was a point made about, "growing understanding of the human element in environmental models". You need to count the human interaction, otherwise it is not a great prediction. High fidelity models making short term predictions were also mentioned. Cross scale interactions between small and big. Back and forth in real time for policy testing, changes and scenarios. There was a point made about an imaginary "one day workshop" where you can run the models fast enough to test lots of different policy implications in one day, rather than having to wait for hours for a model to run. With the UK Covid SEIR models, they were too slow to run even differential equations calibrated on Flu, that Covid predictions ended up being made using an Excel spreadsheet.

In terms of adding another dimension to the model with speed and NetLogo type sliders to make testing changes easy, there was a sugges-

tion that we need a high performance NetLogo machine more than an exascale type machine.

An interesting point about hardware specifications and how local development can't substitute for a real exascale machine was made. Institutional IT policy might dictate that you can't have a GPU laptop and Apple will never have an NVIDIA card, so there are technical limitations to developing for exascale. It is also hard to develop ABM at this level. If research software engineers are trained to develop exascale, then work for an organisation without the requisite hardware, then those skills are lost.

If you had \$1M in funding, what would you spend it on - development time or hardware? The tool chain for exascale is also important. What do you need to deliver results in an acceptable time frame? "Crisp packet modelling" - throw it away once you're done with it. We want to do science, not administration.

This then led into the idea of reusable building blocks that are tested and can be used to build up models, leading to the question of semantic heterogeneity issues for model re-use. Modular and reusable means it is worth investing time in software if you know it is going to be re-used. If the model is bespoke and only used once, then there is no point in spending time and money making it efficient, so exascale could be a technology for running inefficient programs once to get a result.

Transferable skills was mentioned, coming back to what happens to institutions with no GPU access wasting those skills. This was deemed unlikely as this technology is slowly permeating everywhere with Microsoft and Apple now making neural network chips as standard. The question is one of access to people with the right skills. We're going back to teaching people to program in parallel. Platforms and frameworks can mitigate this to an extent as the people writing the models are at a higher level than the low level CUDA parallel execution level.

The most pertinent comment from this whole discussion was simply,

"Time to science"

This is making the point that the development time needs to be taken into account when designing, building, writing, running and analysing the results from exascale models.

Finally, the discussion moved to parameter space, confidence and multiple model runs. There was a general consensus that exascale would allow for more runs and greater confidence, possibly leading to "ABM as a consequence of exascale"? This was a comment that compute speed and batch parallel will give results a confidence factor that validates the technique.

In terms of analysing results, the point was made that exascale has the potential to generate a lot of data very quickly and that this needs to be analysed. Multi-scale modeling could be at the local neighbourhood or down to individual agents or even spatial and temporal scales.

Exascale has a terminal and not a GUI, so is real-time interaction with the data possible? Data can be moved off onto a visualisation machine, sliced and diced and visualised in notebooks with Jupyter notebooks that you can interact with using high performance file system notebooks.

Going from the laptop to HPC is still seen as a problem. The laptop test might be OK, but it goes wrong once you push it to HPC and the greater number of runs shows up an issue that you haven't seen on the laptop. The question is then, "is it doing what we expect?". Rare specific conditions that you don't see in testing at small scale are not picked up by the laptop. Does this lead to more trustworthy and better ABM? Re-use of verified and tested software components can help here.

There was a threat seen as when you make assumptions simply for the sake of the GPU and not for any science reasons. The dynamics of complex adaptive systems was used as an example case. Also, in the HR Department example of Epstein, the calculations might not need parallel processing at all if they are using lookup tables of pre-computed "if X then do Y" type of computations. In other words, simplify and you don't need the parallel.

In conclusion, there are examples of exascale science cases here, with the inclusion of realistic human activity in a model coupling example a more concrete general use case. Climate change examples that include human reactions to change might come under this category, but these types of examples, by their nature, involve collaborations across domains. Emergence effects from large scale ABMs are difficult to demonstrate without an actual example, because they are emergent.

1.6 Strategic Literature Review (SLR)

As part of the ExAMPLER project, a systematic literature review of social science agent-based modelling papers was conducted using the Scopus and Web of Science databases. Keywords were used to identify potential candidate papers in journals, resulting in 54,279 papers from Web of Science and 231,312 papers from Scopus. Filtering was then performed to combine the results from the two databases and remove duplicate papers from the keyword match. The final level of filtering involved setting a threshold which was designed to include journals which had a high probability of matching ABMSS papers based on the keyword results. This needed to take into account the variation in the number of publications for each journal before selecting a journal for inclusion. Some journals were found to have very high publication rates and so would score high numbers of potential papers based on ABMSS related keywords. After the second level of filtering was complete, there were 33 journals selected, resulting in 3,417 papers as candidates for screening.

The screening stage of the SLR involved at least three researchers

reading the title and abstract of all of the 3,417 papers. With five researchers involved, this required reading approximately 2,000 each and answering the following questions based on just the title and abstract:

1. Is this paper about an agent-based model? (A computer simulation of multiple heterogeneous interacting agents.)
2. Does the abstract tell you it is a simulation based on people and/or aggregations of people (i.e. social science)?
3. Does the abstract mention a specific existing population and/or geographical area?

If any of the answers is “no”, then the reviewer is not asked the questions that follow, as the paper is then deemed not to be ABMSS. This resulted in 228 potential ABMSS papers which then went through a further reading of the full paper by the reviewers. This time around, a Google Form was used to fill out information contained in the paper to firstly ascertain that it really is an ABMSS paper and to try to find out more detailed information, like the number of agents, number of simulation runs, computer hardware and representation of space in the model. In total, 161 papers were identified as ABMSS, with just 18 of them stating that high performance computing was used.

The view of the researchers reading the papers was that the majority were describing the science and not the computing that was required to achieve the results. This is confirmed by the HPC part of the review where data on the scientific computing setup used is hard to find. In the sample of 3,417 papers read during the course of the review, there was a lack of HPC use generally, with only 18 papers identified as using HPC.

In order to gauge the size of the models being run from the literature review, the questions for the full read of the paper required the reviewers to fill in information about the number of agents, number of simulation runs and number of steps in a run. The data on the number of agents in models is shown in figure 5. This shows the frequency distribution of the number of agents for desktop PC based models (blue square) versus HPC models (red circle). The smaller number of models using HPC is immediately visible, but the most interesting finding from this data is that the larger models are not exclusively HPC models. The extreme right of the graph shows the 10 million agent column, with PC based modelling at this scale and no HPC. Any papers containing computing benchmarks or timings are extremely rare, so we lack information on how computationally intensive this 10 million agent model is. The raw number of agents is not the whole story as the agent’s computational complexity, the number of steps in the model, the number of runs and the size of the space they occupy are all contributing factors.

Following on from the number of agents, the graph in figure 6 shows the numbers of simulation runs for PC and HPC. These peak at hun-

Figure 5: Distribution of the number of agents in models for PC (blue) and HPC (red). The x-axis shows number of agents from tens (10s) up to ten millions (10Ms). The y-axis shows the count of the number of models found at that level.

dreds of runs (100s), with the highest number of runs for the biggest PC model only going into the hundreds of thousands (100Ks).

By looking back at the original papers, the model with the most agents in figure 5 is “Mitigation Measures for Pandemic Influenza in Italy: An Individual Based Model Considering Different Scenarios” in the journal PlosOne (2008) [Cio+08]. This is an SEIR infection model with 57 million agents representing the total population of Italy. In many models of this general type, it is common to use a subset of the total population and scale up the results, so the first question to ask is where the data on the population of the whole country comes from? In this case, the Census is used to generate a synthetic population for 57 million people, allocated to family groups and geographic regions. This is an important point to note, as it was one of the concerns that came out of the Michigan workshop, where we had the comment, “large scale models require large scale data” and that you can also, “play with the populations to affect the outcome”. Data validation in modelling of this scale is crucial.

Using the SLR data on the number of reported steps in models, the model with the most steps is 6,720,448,000, for “Exploiting Human Resource Requirements to Infer Human Movement Patterns for Use in Modelling Disease Transmission Systems: An Example from Eastern

Figure 6: Distribution of the number of simulation runs performed for the models for PC models (blue) and models using HPC (red). The x-axis shows number model runs from ones (1s) up to hundreds of thousands (100Ks). The y-axis shows the count of the number of models found at that level.

Province, Zambia” in PlosOne (2015) [Ald+15]. Here, the time steps are seconds for a model of human movement where there are 5000 agents and 4200 runs of the model performed for sensitivity analysis. This is labelled as a model using HPC as the authors state that the “Iridis 3 supercomputer at the University of Southampton was used to produce the migration paths for the agents in the ABM to follow”. It is stated that “Two separate computer programs were used to produce the observed results”, and it is unclear from the paper whether the ABM itself used the supercomputer. This shows how difficult it is to classify the hardware being used to implement agent-based models.

To complete the analysis of agents, steps and simulation runs, the model with the highest number of simulation runs from figure 6 is: “A food tax only minimally reduces the N surplus of Swiss agriculture” [Sch+21]. The figure of 482,000 runs comes from the fact that the sensitivity analysis is the crucial part of the paper, which shows the effects of different policy changes on reducing the Nitrogen surplus of 3,300 farms in Switzerland. The paper with the second highest number of simulations runs (360,000) is about Dengue fever transmission in Colombia [Pad+15]. Both papers demonstrate how difficult it is to obtain this information from the paper text. The Nitrogen excess paper figure is based on two formulas given in the text to compute how

many runs are required for a statistically representative sample given the number of factors being tested. The Dengue fever paper is based on multiplying the repetition rate by “288 different combinations of external social-vector exposure, immigration, birth rate and vector production (250 replicates each)” [Pad+15], as stated in the results section. These figures take some working out based on understanding the text, which is why only 115 out of the 3,417 papers have an entry for the number of simulation runs.

Looking in detail at the papers with the highest numbers of agents, highest number of steps and greatest number of model repetition runs, serves to demonstrate how difficult it is to find simple and reliable data on how the model was implemented. The most interesting statistic is to look at how many of the 3,417 papers give any kind of figure for the three model dimensions. Only 121 papers state the number of agents, 114 papers contain the number of steps and 115 contain the number of simulation runs. This equates to approximately 3% of the paper sample and gives weight to the reviewers’ comments about how papers are describing the science behind the model while omitting the computing details. None of these papers at the extreme end of the ABMSS scale provide enough information for somebody else to replicate the model and they only describe the scientific results.

The recommendation from the first part of the SLR is that more use of HPC needs to be made before ABMSS is ready to take the next step up to exascale. There is also an open question of how to determine model complexity? This is something that would be useful to help determine which models are being limited by computing resources and which might benefit from exascale. The number of agents is one factor, but we see 10 million agents running on the CPU and not using HPC. Combining this with the number of steps in the model and then multiplying up by the number of runs required for sensitivity analysis is one possible index of model complexity. However, this does not take into account agent communication overheads, which links to how space is represented in the model and the frequency of agent interaction per model step. This is one area that requires further research.

The other question of interest from the SLR is whether ABM frameworks are being used more extensively or whether models are being written mainly as bespoke pieces of code? This is required by the roadmap as it will inform the recommendations that follow about how the ABMSS community can transition to using exascale. If one or more ABM frameworks are found in the majority of the SLR papers, then it is worth directing efforts into accelerating a particular framework. If the larger scale models are using bespoke code in order to take advantage of faster run times from hand crafted models, then the path to exascale will need to take this into account. The literature review gives no conclusive answer in this case, as both methodologies are being followed to different degrees.

Further analysis of the corpus of 228 screened papers was performed with a keyword search to find the papers where ABM frameworks are mentioned. This is the set of papers that was identified as potentially an ABMSS paper by reading the title and abstract. The keyword search methodology was designed around the using “pdfgrep”³ utility to scan the full paper PDFs for keywords. Fragments of text around the keyword match were used to manually determine whether the match context was correct, for example, is a model really using NetLogo, or do they say something like, “Repast, Netlogo and MASON are ABM frameworks”? The keywords are all searched as case insensitive.

The data from the framework search is shown in table 1. This shows the keywords and the number of occurrences of the keyword in the set of papers.⁴ NetLogo is the most frequent, followed by Repast, MASON and, surprisingly, AnyLogic, MESA, the Julia agents library, GAMA and SWARM. This is good evidence of the use of ABM frameworks, with Net-Logo appearing in 31% of the papers (71/228) identified as ABM papers.

Keyword	Count (228)	Percentage ($\div 228$)
netlogo	71	31.1
repast	19	8.3
mason	8	3.5
anylogic	7	3.1
mesa	3	1.3
agents.jl	2	0.9
gama	2	0.9
swarm	1	0.4

Table 1: Keyword search for ABM frameworks in the SLR papers. Keywords are case insensitive. NOTE: FlameGPU, ChiSim, PDES-MAS, Simudyne and SpatialOS all scored zero.

Evidence for bespoke agent-based modelling papers is harder to find. One potential idea is to filter on the reviewer read papers that were identified as about agent based models and then look for an absence of an ABM framework. However, this is difficult to do in practice as context is important. A bespoke model can still mention a framework and detecting the absence of any framework when our list is non-exhaustive is not possible. The simplest solution is to look at the data from the full read of the papers. Of these, 161 are identified as true ABMSS, but, from table 1, there are a total of 110 papers with frameworks recognised by the keyword search. This means that there are 118 papers remaining, from the original 228, that are either bespoke models, unrecognised frameworks, or rejected as not strictly agent-based modelling and social science of a

³pdfgrep: <https://pdfgrep.org/>

⁴NOTE: the list of frameworks is designed to match the list of frameworks in table 5 later in this roadmap.

real world example. The conclusion is that the sample of non-framework papers being larger than the framework papers is strongly suggesting that bespoke model development and unknown frameworks are a significant part of the literature review. Knowing that these papers have all been identified as about models of some kind, then further analysis of the programming languages being used is worthwhile.

Table 2 shows the keyword search for some popular ABM programming languages. However, this cannot be taken as bespoke development, as Repast uses Java and “PyNetLogo” links python and NetLogo, so these groups overlap with the frameworks. The smaller numbers do suggest a bias towards models using frameworks. NetLogo’s count of 71 is a long way ahead of Java’s 31, which overlaps with Repast and its count of 19. Repast also has a Symphony and HPC variant, which is C++, so figures for bespoke model development are difficult to estimate from programming languages.

Keyword	Count (228)	Percentage ($\div 228$)
java	31	13.5
python	26	11.4
C++	12	5.3
julia	2	0.9
cuda	1	0.4
fortran	0	0.0

Table 2: Keyword search for computer languages in the SLR papers.

The most interesting statistic from the programming language analysis is that only 72 papers out of 228 (31.6%) matched a programming language. As before, this is not an exhaustive list of all possible programming languages, but this is a surprisingly low percentage of coverage.

In summary, the SLR demonstrates the use of frameworks, with NetLogo proving to be the most widely used. Evidence for bespoke development is also found, so the roadmap approach needs to cover both types of model development. However, it is not the case that the bigger models are automatically going to require bespoke programming, as shown by the agent numbers and simulation run numbers in figures 5 and 6. This shows that HPC is under-used in agent-based modelling and social simulation. Whether this is due to a lack of availability of high performance computing, its financial cost, or a lack of HPC expertise, the recommendation is that the ABMSS community will need to step up to the HPC level before being able to make the next step up to exascale.

2 Science Drivers

Very few applications are run for the first time on more than 100,000 threads. In “Agent Based Modelling and Simulation for EXASCALE Computing” [Nor+08], the authors from the Argonne National Laboratory cite examples of how ABMs can be used in the simulation of the electricity markets under different regulatory conditions, cell behaviour in the biological sciences and autonomous robot swarms exploring Mars. In terms of applications to the social simulation area, there are examples of “crowd modelling and human movement”, “evacuation modelling” and “consumer markets and supply chains”. Transport and infrastructure could be included as another possible social simulation area, with people interacting as they move to and from work, school or retail locations.

The key factors for determining whether it is an agent based social simulation model are as follows:

- Is it a simulation or model of people and/or aggregations of people (i.e. social science)? Transport simulations of people travelling in cars (or other vehicles) are included, but not, for example, a new method of traffic light sequencing.
- Is it a computer simulation of multiple heterogeneous interacting agents? If the agents do not interact with each other, or indirectly via a third party mechanism, then it could be a microsimulation model rather than agent based. Examples of agents interacting with their environment which causes interactions with other agents indirectly are included.
- ABMSS looks at: interactions between agents, interactions between agent and environment, decisions made by agent.

This leaves the question of what the science drivers are for moving ABMSS up to extreme scale? In [DL07] from 2007, D’Souza and Ly-senko scale the original 1996 “SugarScape” model of Epstein and Axtell [EA96] up to 1 million agents. By 2009, Epstein is simulating 6.5 billion agents using his “Global Scale Agent Based Model (GSAM)” [Eps09] in preparation for a global swine flu epidemic (H1N1). Following on from the COVID19 pandemic in 2019, modelling the interactions of people across the whole world and disease transmission has a direct benefit to all. However, as Epstein states in [Eps09], “Agents can be made to behave something like real people: prone to error, bias, fear” and “...who adapt their behaviours — perhaps irrationally — based on disease prevalence.”. The point is also made that ABMs need to be run multiple times (batch parallel) in order to obtain a confidence interval as these simulations can include agents who make stochastic decisions, or have different starting conditions due to data accuracy or there are

different decisions made following on from policy scenarios which need to be tested. An agent based model is more of an ensemble of possible output states derived from a set of starting conditions.

In the report, “UK Research & Innovation: Science case for UK Supercomputing” ([Wil+20]), which is published on the Excalibur website, the authors make the science case for supercomputing in all areas of academia and industry. Section 8 of the report, on “digital humanities and social sciences”, contains information most relevant to agent based modelling and social science:

“The way in which evidence-based social and governmental decisions are made could be made considerably more efficient and effective if supercomputing power capable of analysing and modelling vast amounts of data could be made available. Greater computing power and the new supply of data will enable us to better understand society, and ensure that the UK is well placed to exploit future developments in this rapidly changing arena.”

- (David de Roure, Andrew Prescott [Wil+20][Ch8])

Agent based modelling at scale is mentioned in section 8.6, “Computational modelling for decision-making”:

“To focus on one with immediate exascale demand, agent-based modelling codes have been developed for supercomputers and clusters and used in multiple disciplines. These contain large sets of agents that each represent individuals or groups, with differing levels of autonomy, different characteristics and different behaviours. Large scale simulations enable modellers to explore emergent properties, or predict when tipping points will be reached.”

- (David de Roure, Nigel Gilbert [Wil+20][Ch8.6])

This also highlights the 2018 Blackett Review, “Computational modelling: technological futures” [Wal+18], which is a Government report on the future place of computational modelling in the UK. Two of the chapters are directly relevant to social science modelling and ABM, “Chapter 5, Modelling in Public Policy” and “Chapter 7, Modelling Cities and Infrastructure”. In the public policy chapter, three examples are provided of examples where social science agent based modelling can be used: “Future Risk from Flooding in the UK”, “Using Modelling in Civil Emergencies” and “Can you build a model to predict homelessness from childhood?”. The civil emergencies and flood risk models provide excellent examples of why the capability to do exascale modelling in the UK is essential. In the event of civil unrest, pandemic or other environmental disaster, having our own compute resource means we do not have

to waste time trying to procure a computer to run our models in a time critical situation.

Using models to make difficult decisions goes back to the first of the recommendations from the Blackett report. Using models is about making evidence based decisions, not relying on the experience or bias of the elected decision maker:

Recommendation 1: Decision-makers should consider how analysis using models might be able to help in making difficult decisions.

- (Blackett Report [Wal+18][pp8])

As a downside, though, it gives the politician the ability to blame the computer model if it all goes wrong. The model is the due diligence. There is a financial implication here, too, because a verified and approved for use model which can be run on a Government owned computer is very cheap to use. Commissioning a report from a consulting company in order to comply with due diligence regulations before taking a decision is usually extremely expensive. An open question is how much Government spends on external consultants, compared to building re-usable and reliable compute resources which can answer the same questions faster?

The justification for ABMSS is in the final paragraph of the executive summary and recommendations (pp12):

“And finally, decision-makers in the public and private sectors are making extremely important decisions about complex human and natural systems. If they are to make good decisions, they need the best decision support. Computational modelling matters.”

- (Blackett Report [Wal+18][pp12])

The “UKRI Science Case for Supercomputing” document from 2020 [Wil+20] also cites the importance of academic social supercomputing and the Swiss use of a 0.44 exaflop computer facility:

“Social simulation increasingly appears in the project portfolios of major supercomputing centres, for example the 440 TF (TeraFlop) facility in ETH, Zurich, is used to support “social supercomputing” applications”.

- ([Wil+20][pp78])

To quote from their vision statement:

“**Vision:** In order to deal with an increasingly complex world, we need ever more sophisticated computational models that can help us make decisions wisely and understand the potential consequences of choices.” - (David de Roure, Nigel Gilbert [Wil+20][Ch8.6])

In the section on, “New and Emerging Forms of Data”, Birkin and de Roure suggest how some of the key research challenges can apply directly to Government policy and drive economic development:

“Key research challenges: Analysis: How can we derive inferences, often in real-time, from billions of data points relating to patterns of movement, social interaction or economic behaviour? **Design:** How do we design complex systems which combine the interactions between billions of agents (both human and physical) to deliver next generation technologies e.g. mobility as a service, combining vehicles, sensors, people and infrastructure to deliver socially beneficial outcomes? **Policy:** How can we manage interventions to deliver economic benefits, quality of life, healthy or sustainable environments, using New and Emerging Forms of Data (NEFD) in combination with e.g. deep learning, massive ensembles or data assimilation to validate policy conclusions? These challenges require innovation in streaming data analytics, privacy-enhancing technologies, and data linkage at scale.”

- (Mark Birkin, David de Roure [Wil+20][Ch8.8])

Large scale Government infrastructure projects may provide the science case for exascale computing, in addition to a financial one. Projects like High Speed 2, Crossrail and East West Rail benefit from computer modelling of large numbers of people and transport infrastructure. The latest Government plan to build 1.5 million homes in 5 years, or plans to expand an airport involve modelling millions of people travelling between home and work, or home and retail. If there are 8 billion people in the world, then is this the upper limit? For an evolving infectious disease emergency, whole Earth modelling of interactions between people in real-time can have immediate health and financial benefits. However, transactions between people can exceed the number of interactions in space, so this may be the real limiting factor, for example modelling a country’s economy? Alternatively, batch parallel and confidence measures might be the science driver and enabling technology when doing exascale ABMSS? This was discussed in the iEMSS workshop in Michigan, where the idea that being able to perform multiple runs of a model to explore the output space more fully and obtain an accurate confidence metric would be the driver for exascale ABMSS. Cross cutting models and “human in the climate loop” all featured as science drivers discussed at iEMSS, where a human modelling element is added to a physics based pure science model in order to make the model a more realistic prediction of the real world. An example which was used was a climate model where humans are adapting their behaviour to a changing climate, which is changing in response to the behaviour of the humans.

In summary, science drivers for an exascale computer have been identified which come from the ability to react to emergencies in real-time e.g. pandemics, “human in the loop models” e.g. climate and policy modelling “what if” scenarios e.g. building 1.5 million homes or transport scenarios. The true science case for funding an exascale computer may be a financial one?

3 Timeline

The two exascale computers that are currently operational are the Oak Ridge, “Frontier”, computer (2022) and the Argonne National Labs’, “Aurora”, computer (2024). The next exascale computer slated to become operation is the U.S. Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory’s, “El Capitan”, in late 2024, followed by the European, “Jupiter”, computer in 2025. As the UK Government has cancelled the upgrade of the ARCHER computer to exascale, the most likely route to UK researchers accessing exascale is likely to come from the European “Jupiter” computer at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre. This suggests that UK ABM researchers looking to scale up to exascale have around 12 months before the first applications start running on it, although a 10 rack pilot machine called “JETI” is currently being tested with example workloads as part of the commissioning process. This is stated to be exactly 8% of the full system, achieving 83 petaflops on benchmarks, so the “Jupiter” computer is projected to only just break the 1 exaflop performance barrier.

Based on the 12 month estimate before a European exascale computer is available, how can this time be used and what needs to be done to make agent-based modelling and social simulation ready to make use of the new resource? The GANTT chart in figure 3 shows an example of how this could be achieved.

The blue bars show the tasks for model builders, while the green tasks are for research software engineers. The magenta bars indicate periods of testing or benchmarking on real computers. The meaning of each of the tasks is defined as follows:

“Identify Models” is a literature review of models which are either already targeting HPC or GPU architectures, or those which could benefit from scaling up. This has already been started as part of the ExAMPLER Systematic Literature Review (SLR).

“HPC/GPU Testing” test and benchmark large-scale agent-based models running on CPU based HPC systems and GPU based desktop systems and GPU server clusters.

“GPU Desktop” is a task spanning the whole year and is a continuing effort to make best use of the hardware available on desktop systems, principally models making use of gaming GPU cards and

Figure 7: Timeline for Exascale ABMSS adoption based on the European Jupiter computer’s installation schedule. Blue bars show model development work, magenta bars show testing and benchmarking on real computers and green bars show Research Software Engineer development work.

acceleration. A mid-level GPU laptop computer could now achieve a teraflop in processing power.

“RSE - frameworks” requires research software engineer (RSE) support to investigate the potential for moving existing frameworks like NetLogo and Repast onto GPU architectures. This will include the feasibility of taking the model code from one system and converting it to run on a GPU enabled one e.g. NetLogo, ReLogo, Repast and FlameGPU or MASS CUDA.

“RSE - proxy apps” build and benchmark proxy apps for agent-based models to determine exascale performance. This will develop into knowledge about best practices for developing models for exascale.

“Step-up Test” assumes that partly built exascale machines will be available for testing as part of the build and commissioning process of the full computer. Typically, reduced numbers of cabinets have been tested prior to building up into the full configuration e.g. Crusher for Frontier and Jeti for Jupiter. By having proxy apps for

ABM available, we can benchmark early and use this as evidence later on when bidding for time on the full machine.

4 Background

The top 500 list⁵ contains the statistics for the fastest computers currently known in the world. Table 3 and table 4 shows a list of the currently installed and proposed exascale implementations, including Frontier, which was the first exascale leader on the TOP 500 list, installed in 2022. Also included for reference are the ARCHER2 computer, which is the current fastest UK supercomputer, and Isambard-3, which is the proposed new AI research computer and which is only petascale.

Name	Country	Organisation	Operational Date
Frontier	US	ORNL	2022
El Capitan	US	LLNL	2024
Aurora	US	Argonne	2024
Jupiter	EU	Julich Inst.	proposed 2025?
Sunway Oceanlite	China	-	2021?
TIANHE-3	China	-	2021?
ARCHER2	UK	EPCC	2021
Isambard-3	UK	Bristol	2024
ARCHER3	UK	EPCC	(cancelled)

Table 3: List of Exascale computers. NOTE: ARCHER2 and Isambard-3 are not exascale.

Name	ExFLOPS	MWatts	Cores (GPU/CPU)
Frontier	1.194	21	8,335,360 / 606,208
El Capitan	1.742	40	10,156,032 (APU MI300A)
Aurora	2.0	60	8,159,232 / 1,189,888
Jupiter	1.0	15	350M? est / 1,728,000
Sunway Oceanlite	1.03	35	0 / 42M
TIANHE-3	1.3	TBA	?
ARCHER2	0.02	1.2	0 / 750,080
Isambard-3	0.003	0.27	0 / 55,000
ARCHER3	TBA	30	(cancelled)

Table 4: List of Exascale computer specifications. NOTE: ARCHER2 and Isambard-3 are not exascale. Jupiter core numbers are estimated from proposed specifications.

⁵Top 500 website: <https://www.top500.org/>

Mohr ([Moh11]) provides a review of languages used on high performance computers. This shows that C/C++ is the most common language, but also notes the usage of Python and Java. In terms of accelerators, OpenCL is mentioned, but CUDA is the leader.

Electricity prices dictate how much an hour of exascale computing costs, which are subject to market fluctuations. The first generation of exascale computers, for example Frontier (21MW), El Capitan (40MW) and Aurora (60MW), are using more power than current petascale computers, for example the previous top 500 list number 1, Fugaku, with 442 petaflops and 30MW power consumption. More typical for petascale machines is power consumption around the 10MW region. The UK's Isambard-3 supercomputer is 2.7 petaflops and 270KW, while Archer 2 is 19.54 petaflops and 1.2MW.

Flops per watt is a more useful statistic and is tracked by the "Green 500" list⁶. Exascale computers *might* start to consistently out-perform peta scale as accelerated processors like the H100 become mainstream. The Microsoft Eagle computer, which is Top 3 in November 2023, uses this technology, as do the NVIDIA DGX computers, which are used extensively for AI research.

4.1 The International Exascale Software Project (IESP) Roadmap

Between 2009 and 2012, the International Exascale Software Project ran a series of 8 meetings in Santa Fe (USA), Paris (France), Tsukuba (Japan), Oxford (UK), Maui (Hawaii), San Francisco (USA), Cologne (Germany) and Kobe (Japan). The outcome of these meetings and workshops was the IESP roadmap document [DBa11].

The following points are taken from that roadmap:

- Tools, Algorithms, Software and Models need to be developed for exascale
- Is there a Software Roadmap?
- There is the need to agree a destination based on background experience - where are we needing to get to?
- Allow leading edge ABM to exploit extreme scale computing – what is the "X-STACK" that makes this possible?
- Scaling up and down – desktop to HPC to exascale – step up to run and step down to test
- Modular, open software, not tied to single author/vendor – this is risk adverse

⁶Green 500 list: <https://top500.org/lists/green500/>

- System clocks are 0.5-4GHZ, typically 2GHZ. Does instruction level parallelism (ILP) enable exascale? Data movement across memory = power used
- Can we simulate running on exascale, or use a step-up computer? Need benchmarks and proxy apps to refine performance.
- What are the programming models for GPGPU? Parallel at different levels e.g. ILP/GPU/Memory/Rack
- Evolutionary or revolutionary – do we throw away the existing software and start again or can we evolve to exascale?
- Is debugging too costly?
- With 10^8 or 10^9 threads, a 1000^3 mesh has one point per thread – does this lead to large 3D or 2D simulation applications, or is it better to run smaller batches of simpler simulations?
- Eliminate synchronisation points and barriers? Is this possible?
- Data visualisation on large outputs – how to identify features of interest in petabytes of data?
- Spread work to parallelise, but localise to keep minimal latency
- Exascale software resilience and faults - is the software going to have to be resilient enough to deal with hardware faults? Given the amount of hardware required for exascale, complexity dictates that the software will see faults happening in real-time
- FLOPS are cheap, but moving data around is expensive - is this the limiting factor?
- Reproducibility - for somebody else to reproduce the results they are going to need an exascale computer and appropriate software. This limits the ability to do reproducible science. Results might also not be consistent across runs on the same hardware, even with a deterministic model. The extreme parallelism might cause an unacceptable variability in results.
- Co-Design Vehicle (CDV) - the three elements of science, software and hardware need to all come together. Scientists have a problem to solve, software engineers code it efficiently and hardware experts design the architecture for it to run on, while feeding back to the software team.

4.2 European Exascale Software Initiative (EESI) Roadmap

The European exascale software project (EuroHPC) produced a roadmap document in 2015, which can be accessed from this link: <http://www.eesi-project.eu/at-works/roadmaps/>

This outlined three pillars as follows:

- Tools and Programming Models
- Ultra Scalable Algorithms
- Data Centric Approach

The European exascale software initiative is building on an existing group of petascale computers distributed around the countries of the European Union. These EuroHPC computers include “LUMI” (Finland), “Leonardo” (Italy), “MareNostrum 5” (Spain), “MeluXina” (Luxembourg), “Karolina” (Czechia), “Discoverer” (Bulgaria), “Vega” (Slovenia) and “Deucalion” (Portugal). The purpose of this project is to build an exascale computer at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC) in Germany. Called “JUPITER”⁷, it is described as a modular supercomputer and the first module (a single rack) was installed in May 2024, called “Jedi”. This is an NVIDIA GH200 (Grace Hopper) based architecture with 24,000 GH superchips. Final installation is planned for 2025.

4.3 The Exascale Project and Proxy Apps

The Exascale Project website contains current news on exascale developments and also on proxy apps: <https://www.exascaleproject.org/> and <https://proxyapps.exascaleproject.org/>.

Exascale proxy applications are like benchmarks, except that a proxy application is intended to be a real piece of code that solves a typical scientific problem, for example run a self-contained computational fluid dynamics model. In contrast, a benchmark is an artificial test of performance for example, multiply and add a million double precision floats and time how long it takes. Proxy apps are needed to test the performance of *real* design patterns and to enable improvements to be made that then filter down to the full scale scientific applications.

The aim of this section is to answer the following question:

“What existing design patterns for agent based social simulation models already exist on exascale?”

⁷JUPITER: Joint Undertaking Pioneer for Innovative and Transformative Exascale Research.

The following is a summary of a few of the Exascale project proxy apps which might be relevant to agent based modelling and social simulation:

Language: Python or Python and C++

DeepCAM is a PyTorch application which trains a deep learning model for extreme weather identification in climate predictions. This won the Gordon Bell prize in 2018.

Dimenet++ is the other Python application which is also machine learning. Both of these proxy apps are benchmarking applications which are used to test methods and techniques used in the full scale code.

CANDLE benchmarks - Machine learning, building a single scalable deep neural network code called CANDLE (CANCer Distributed Learning Environment). and FlexFlow - Candle Uno - accelerate LLMS?

MiniRL - reinforcement learning

cosmoflow - training a 3D convolutional neural network on N-body cosmology simulation data to predict physical parameters of the universe.

miniGAN - The GAN's generator and discriminator generate plausible 2D/3D maps and identify fake maps, respectively. Related applications exist in cosmology (CosmoFlow, ExaGAN) and wind energy (ExaWind).

Kernels for FFTX - FFT and other discrete Fourier methods.

Language: C++ and C (lots, so selected what looks relevant)

MCB The Monte Carlo Benchmark (MCB) is a proxy for the computational performance of Monte Carlo algorithms on parallel architectures.

Chatterbug A suite of communication-intensive proxy applications that mimic commonly found communication patterns in HPC codes. These codes can be used as synthetic codes for benchmarking, or for trace generation using OTF2.

miniVite miniVite is a proxy application that implements a single phase of Louvain method in distributed memory for graph community detection.

IAMR Navier Stokes solver

miniAero Navier Stokes solver

NVIDIA CUDA is also mentioned as a language, but the two applications listed are already in the C/C++ and Python catalogues. The use of CUDA directly to code agent based models is too time intensive for development of a one off bespoke model. Similarly, frameworks like Tensorflow and PyTorch, which are used in proxy apps for neural network applications, can be re-purposed as more general accelerators for mathematically oriented scientific programming with vectors and matrix data. In amongst the other proxy apps, there is also a mix of chemistry, materials science, genetics, cosmology and astrophysics, which are outside of our knowledge. It is difficult to tell what the algorithms would be doing and whether there is a design pattern that would be useful for agent based modelling.

Looking at an overview of all the proxy apps, there is a split between the AI/ML training (e.g. it's done in a library like Tensorflow or PyTorch) and the mathematical solver applications (e.g. aerodynamics applications). In combination with this are the benchmark apps that are designed to test a specific code pattern e.g. chatterbug message passing or MCB for Monte Carlo simulation tests.

This suggests two things for ABMSS: firstly, it should be possible to accelerate a library that is commonly used by agent based models, like Repast HPC or FlameGPU. Secondly, what is needed is a proxy app that shows performance on the sort of bespoke code that gets run in agent based models, or at least, a proxy app using a segment of an HPC ABM framework. One issue here is with NetLogo models which are Java and would depend on accelerating the Java virtual machine. This comes back to the issue of explicit acceleration, where JVM accelerators like TornadoVM require hints in the Java code to show where parallelism is possible. This type of pattern is not covered in any of the proxy apps and is a big problem to implement with NetLogo ABMs. A more favourable roadmap would appear to be to take the NetLogo code and convert it to another framework, for example PyLogo [AL21], ReLogo [Ozi+13], or alternatively, use a formal description model like ODD [Gri+20] to describe the model and then let the computer re-write it for the target architecture.

Finally, the clear conclusion here is that an agent based modelling proxy app is required. This is needed to enable researchers to test performance of different design patterns to optimise for exascale. The requirement is for a model that can scale the number of agents, control the degree of interaction between agents and simulate agents that require a large amount of compute per simulation cycle ("fat agents"). During discussions, Watson and Lovelock's Daisyworld was suggested as a benchmark [WL83]. Alternatively, Epstein's Sugarscape [EA96] is another example that has been used extensively as a benchmark.

5 Paths Towards Exascale Agent Based Social Simulation

This section of the roadmap breaks down the critical requirements for an exascale software stack for agent based social simulation. This is categorised into the following six sections:

- Software: bespoke or ABM frameworks? Programming languages.
- Hardware: architecture dependence, acceleration and power.
- Messaging: Agent Communications and Physical Interconnect.
- Batch parallel, model parallel and sensitivity analysis.
- Visual Analytics and Spatial Data: results and looking for interesting features in petabytes of data.
- Development Environment and Step-up Machines.

5.1 Software: Bespoke Agent Based Modelling Programs

The Systematic Literature Review and subsequent background research identified agent based models being written in Python (Repast Symphony), C++ (FlameGPU etc), Java (Repast and NetLogo) and possibly Julia ([DVD22]). Of these, C++ and Julia look promising for scaling up to exascale, as there are Exascale Proxy apps already targeting these languages. Python was used more for workflow orchestration or data visualisation in Proxy Apps. However, it is a language worth exploring, but probably in conjunction with more optimised code written in another language. The use of the ‘Numba’ library⁸ for accelerating Python code has been mentioned previously, although this is not exascale acceleration. The theoretical problem of how to optimise agent based models for exascale when GPU accelerators are designed for matrix and vector operations is a difficult one. In “Julia as a unifying end-to-end workflow language on the Frontier exascale system” [God+23], the authors implement a Gray-Scott diffusion reaction simulation based on differential equations. This is based around a matrix system, which is well suited to the GPU acceleration architecture. To quote the authors of what is reported to be the first GPU ABM, Sugarscape on Steroids [DL07]:

“While the simulation performance of GPUs is phenomenal, programming them is completely counterintuitive”

While the original paper was written in 2007, GPU programming technology has matured beyond having to program shaders and texture

⁸For Numba see: <https://numba.pydata.org/>

buffers directly as we now have general purpose compute languages like CUDA and HIPS available and usable from within programming languages like C++, Python and Julia. However, there is still a barrier to entry and a steep learning curve, making bespoke agent based models accessible only to people willing to invest a significant amount of time in the software development. This comes back to the “time to science” quote from before, but there may be a way around this by looking at the acceleration of the underlying libraries that are being used by bespoke ABMs. Cellular Automata, for example, Conway’s Game of Life [Gam70], are based on matrix representations and compute kernels exist to accelerate the implementation on GPU hardware [Fuj+15]. Network algorithms like shortest paths and community detection also exist in the CUDA examples library. Any ABM implementation making extensive use of these libraries will see some speedup through GPU acceleration, depending on how effectively they can scale across processing nodes as the model size increases.

For models that are only run once in order to obtain a high value scientific result, a long software development time is probably uneconomic. If the only way to obtain a result in a reasonable time frame requires exascale, then that development time can be justified. Otherwise it is probably easier to simply run *bad* code on a fast machine. The other factor to consider is how the model scales up as either the number of agents is increased, or the communication goes up. A model running with only 10% of the real population on a laptop might show emergent behaviour when run with 100% of the total population on an exascale machine. There is a specific scaling problem when coding a model to run on a single laptop and then expecting it to run across multiple nodes of an exascale machine. This requires inter-process communication which adds a degree of latency. The speedup from the extra compute nodes has to exceed the communication latency, which is likely to require some degree of code optimisation specific to the hardware. Debugging and tuning on exascale is time-consuming and expensive, which is where step-up machines are essential.

The final point relevant to bespoke ABM programs concerns compilers, intermediate languages and virtual machine environments. The workshops have shown NetLogo to be a popular language for ABMS, but the route from a NetLogo model running in a Java Virtual Machine (JVM) on a laptop to an exascale class computer is not an easy one. The JVM could be GPU accelerated, but options like “TornadoVM”⁹ require explicit directives in the code to define what can be parallelised. Similarly, for Python alternatives like Numba and JAX there are extra directives and replacements to code required. It is also worth mentioning “AgentSpeak(L)” [Rao96], which was designed to be a dedicated programming language for writing ABMs, but which has not shown up

⁹For TornadoVM see: <https://www.tornadovm.org/>

in any of our literature reviews. Also, the ODD+D protocol [Gri+06] for defining agent based models which is mentioned in many of the literature review papers as a formal specification of the paper’s model structure. One design pattern for exascale ABM might be to use the definition of the model, whether a NetLogo program or ODD+D document, and computer generate an efficient exascale implementation. The LLVM architecture used by the Julia language to generate intermediate code which is then used to re-target to a GPU architecture is relevant here.

In conclusion, if the bespoke ABM can be modified to make extensive use of a library which is already GPU enabled, then that is a possible route to exascale. Examples of this are Python programs making use of Numba or JAX to accelerate NumPy, or TensorFlow to accelerate matrix operations or run large neural networks. NetLogo programs might be usable via transpilation into a new language like C++ or Julia. A fast, GPU accelerated, JVM would be useful, but would not necessarily yield high performance at the higher application level, depending on how the NetLogo program was written. Bespoke new development is likely to lead to the highest performance ABMs on exascale, but at the expense of long development times. Using a low level library like CUDA or PyCUDA is abstracting hardware specific code too far away from the science logic within the ABM, so Julia then starts to look attractive for new development due to its transformative architecture. Design patterns for how to write good exascale ABM models are needed, so there is a requirement for proxy apps which the ABM community can optimise and include into their own bespoke science models.

5.2 Software: Agent Based Modelling Frameworks

Table 5 contains a list of the main agent based modelling frameworks that have come out of the literature review and workshops. In “Agent Based Modelling and Simulation tools: A review of the state-of-art software” [Aba+17], the authors publish a comprehensive survey of ABM toolkits, including a diagram on what scale they apply at. Repast HPC, Matsim, PDES-MAS and swarm make it to extreme scale, while the list of frameworks that didn’t make it includes: Matsim (microsimulation), UrbanSim (microsimulation), AgentScript (Javascript, not extreme scale). While this is now rather dated, having been published in 2017, it provides a useful reference.

What is harder to quantify is how difficult a job it would be to convert an existing model from using bespoke code to using an existing ABM framework, or converting from one framework to another. If the literature review shows that the easiest path to exascale ABM is to use a framework designed for GPU acceleration, then the issue of conversion between languages, frameworks and transpilation becomes important. This is something that the ABM community has already experienced

with paths for scaling up to HPC. For example, “Relogo” is designed to make the transition from “NetLogo” to Repast and HPC easier [Ozi+13]. However, these resources are over 10 years old and the Systematic Literature Review is not picking up current use.

The list of frameworks in table 5 is designed to capture whether the framework has run on HPC (i.e. REPAST HPC has papers on supercomputer runs), the licence type so we know if it’s commercial and costs money, the language (Python/C++ etc) and the date of latest version so we know if it’s current (i.e. SWARM is not being maintained).

In addition to modelling frameworks, there are other applications that are also useful for running scientific workflows:

- RAY (<https://www.ray.io/>), “Effortlessly scale your complex workloads”.
- SLURM (<https://slurm.schedmd.com>) “Slurm is an open source, fault-tolerant, and highly scalable cluster management and job scheduling system for large and small Linux clusters”.
- TensorFlow (<https://www.tensorflow.org>) “TensorFlow makes it easy to create ML models that can run in any environment”.
- PyTorch (<https://pytorch.org>) “PyTorch is an optimized tensor library for deep learning using GPUs and CPUs”.
- FABSIM3 (<https://fabsim3.readthedocs.io/en/latest>) “generic automation toolkit with plug-ins for different modelling domains and ensemble jobs”.

These fall into the categories of job scheduling and workflow management and GPU acceleration libraries for numerical algorithms (ML and ANN). Job scheduling is worth mentioning in the context of parameter sweeps for model runs and sensitivity analysis. TensorFlow and PyTorch are mentioned here, as they offer a valid design pattern for GPU accelerated matrix and vector operations. If ABMs are able to make extensive use of libraries like these, then we might already have something that we can use which is optimised for GPU and TPU? These libraries are good for parallel numeric algorithms.

One point worth making here is that we currently lack any data on whether models should be developed as bespoke code, or using a framework, as we currently lack a step-up machine to do any testing on. This data will be essential in how we proceed with a roadmap to exascale ABM. In the case of bespoke code development, there are many optimisations available to the developer, while, with model development inside a framework, code optimisation might be far more restricted, with major improvements needed to come from modifying the framework itself.

Name	Licence	GPU?	Organisation	Link
REPAST Symphony	“New BSD”	-	Argonne National Labs	https://repast.github.io/repast_symphony.html
REPAST HPC	“New BSD”	-	Argonne National Labs	https://repast.github.io/repast_hpc.html
REPAST4Py	“New BSD”	-	Argonne National Labs	https://repast.github.io/repast4py.site/index.html
FLAME GPU	MIT	Y	University of Sheffield	https://flamegpu.com/
chiSIM	Custom ANL Open	-	Argonne National Labs	https://github.com/Repast/chiSIM
NetLogo	GPLv2	-	Northwestern University	https://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/
SWARM	open?	-	?	https://www.swarm.org
Simudyne	Commercial	-	Simudyne	https://www.simudyne.com/technology/agent-based-modeling/
MASON	open source	-	George Mason	https://cs.gmu.edu/~eclab/projects/mason/
GAMA	GPLv3	-	IRD/SU France	https://gama-platform.org/
MESA	Apache2	-	Academics	https://mesa.readthedocs.io/en/stable/
SpatialOS	Commercial	Y	Improbable	https://github.com/spatialos
AnyLogic	Commercial	-	AnyLogic	https://www.anylogic.com/
MASS CUDA	Open?	Y	University of Washington	https://depts.washington.edu/dslab/MASS/
PDES-MAS	BSD3	-	Private?	https://pdes-mas.github.io/

Table 5: List of ABM frameworks.

Finally, some of the toolkits on the list have commercial licences. Does this rule them out, as code modification is not possible and publishing repeatable science is a problem? Having large companies con-

trol what gets run on exascale was a problem that was flagged up by the IESP roadmap [DBa11].

5.3 Software: Languages

For a review of languages available and what is required for ABM, we have the review of supercomputer software resources and development stack, including compilers, from Mohr in 2011 [Moh11]. There is also the sample of the Frontier Proxy Apps, which is current. In addition to this, there is the literature review which provides evidence for which languages are being used by ABMSS researchers who write scientific papers. One final piece of evidence can be inferred from the Bell prize competition for supercomputing applications. Papers and code are available for download and this shows the languages being used by researchers targeting high performance applications, although not in the ABM domain.

Based on the fact that the literature review was picking up lots of models in the JASSC journal based on Netlogo, there is a requirement to investigate how hard this would be to achieve at exascale. The following three step plan to get Netlogo models working on exascale is based on the earlier idea of “evolution or revolution”:

- Netlogo uses the JVM, so use an accelerated JVM - easy to get lots of models working fast, but not very well. TornadoVM is an option, but GPU offloading needs to be explicit.
- Use an automatic tool to re-code Netlogo into something else - gets stuff working, but probably not accelerated very well.
- Throw it away and start again, hard option requiring effort, but delivering results.

While intended for Netlogo, the following might also apply to interpreted languages, or other languages that use a runtime or just in time compilation, for example .net intermediate language (IL) and C# or managed C++.

By accelerating the runtime, there is an easy win in terms of getting lots of models running quickly and only having to modify the runtime code. This was the original purpose of Java, “write once, run anywhere”. However, the code structure of the models is unlikely to suit the massively parallel GPU architecture of the exascale computer and this will limit performance. More information on the feasibility is this idea is required for a complete analysis.¹⁰

The next option of transpilation from Netlogo (or another ABM language) into something more suited to exascale parallelisation needs to

¹⁰NOTE: most of the Netlogo codebase is actually Scala rather than Java: <https://github.com/NetLogo/NetLogo> .

be considered. This could also take the form of converting from one framework to another, rather than from one form of bespoke code to another, or, in fact, any permutation of the two. At the current time, there are no hard statistics on what the best target language or architecture is for exascale ABM. The literature review has shown Relogo to be an attempt to run Netlogo programs on Repast HPC, but the fact that most papers are from 10 years ago has to be taken as significant. It might be that this option requires so much programming effort as to make new development from scratch a more viable option. What is needed are some proxy app type samples of ABM code to try this out with.

The final option of starting from scratch and writing a new model might seem like a lot of effort, except for the fact that agent based models tend to be fairly small programs. They're not like having to re-code a wordprocessor with lots of features and a user interface. Combine this with the amount of bespoke code development that was picked up in the literature review and the workshops, and this would probably be the best route for a model not bound to any framework? The key issue is whether the language it is developed in is suitable for exascale, but this can be mitigated if sections can be re-written and accelerated in a modular fashion. It comes back to software development tools and code optimisation.

To finish off the languages section, it is worth picking up on the "time to science" quote from the Michigan workshop. If you are creating a model or library that is going to be reused thousands of times, do you include the software development time in the "time to science"? Probably not, but for models that are run once in order to get an answer, then running bad code is more acceptable. These are the two fundamentally different requirements for exascale ABM, which determine the software development path to be taken.

5.4 Hardware: Architecture, Acceleration, and Power

Without the benefit of a reference architecture, there can be no accurate benchmarks or performance tests. The Frontier architecture is based around a compute node with four AMD Radeon MI250X GPUs and one AMD EPYC 7453 Trento 64 core 2GHz CPU. Memory is shared between CPU and GPUs, which is crucial for speed of transfer. The El Capitan computer is similar, but uses the AMD MI300A "chiplet" APU, which integrates 24 Zen4 CPU cores into a CDNA3 based GPU. The European exascale computer, Jupiter, has four NVIDIA GH200 "superchips" per node with each GH200 chip comprising one Hopper GPU (H100) and one Grace CPU. This means we have both NVIDIA and Radeon GPUs in multiple different configurations. Writing software to target a specific exascale computer may not be so well optimised for a different exascale

computer and benchmarks need to be run across the different architectures to classify the strengths and weaknesses. One interesting point worth mentioning is that software for Frontier is being developed in CUDA, despite the GPU being Radeon, with programs having to be converted using the HIPIFY¹¹ utility. This is encouraging as it shows an immediate architecture agnostic approach to accelerator programming. Ideally, ABM development should not have to be at this low a level in the software stack, as there need to be frameworks and libraries to make life easier for the model developer. Parallel programming is going to be essential in order to make best use of the machine.

A simplified description of an agent based model could be described as follows:

```

For all agents:
    Query environment/Communicate with other agents
    Update Agent Internal State
Repeat

```

The communication phase is key, as this is difficult to parallelise, being a complex system.

The model consists of N agents, taking A_i seconds to query/communicate any agent interactions and A_t seconds to compute their next step state, run over S steps of a simulation. The total run time, T_{run} is shown in equation 1.

$$T_{run} = SN(A_i + A_t) \quad (1)$$

Over a single time step, this block synchronous programming model is always waiting for the longest running agent to complete before starting on the next time step. This isn't necessarily true, as steps can be interleaved between non-interacting agents, but this serves as a first simple model of performance.

Running over an 8 million thread processor we would aim for an 8 million times speedup in T_{run} for the pure parallel case. Amdahl's law (equation 2) gives the expected speedup for the case where a percentage of the compute time is serial, for example waiting for all the agents to complete their time step updates before moving onto the next step.

$$Speedup = \frac{1}{(1 - p) + \frac{p}{s}} \quad (2)$$

Amdahl's law: s =speedup e.g. 8 million processors, p =proportion benefiting from speedup e.g. 0.9=90% parallel.

¹¹HIP: <https://github.com/ROCm-Developer-Tools/HIP> and HIPIFY: <https://github.com/ROCm-Developer-Tools/HIPIFY>

Putting $s = 8000000$ and $p = 0.9$ into equation 2, we only get a potential speedup of ≈ 10 . In order to take full advantage of the exascale computer's parallelism with 8 million processing threads, the degree of parallelism needs to be close to 1.0. This is shown in the graph of figure 8 for 99% parallel, 95% and 90%. The graph shows that, for an application with 95% benefiting from acceleration, the speedup tends to 20 after only about 512 processors.

Figure 8: Amdahl Exascale. 99% parallelism (blue line) results tends to only a 100 times speedup after about 4096 processors.

The key to accelerating an agent based model is in predicting what the percentage of code benefiting from parallelism (p) actually is. This is difficult to do generally, because it relies on knowing how much memory contention and blocking occurs when agents are querying for interactions with other agents in the simulation. The best we can do is to say that there is a computational element to the agent updating which inherently parallel, A_t , while the interaction element, A_i is unknown because this is the part that makes an agent based model a complex system. The recommendation is that this is a factor that needs to be measured empirically for different model programs using a step up computer. By testing on a single node computer, then moving up to a multiple node computer, the difference in the run times allows for estimation of the p factor, which can be used to estimate performance when scaling all the way up to exascale.

In terms of the order of A_i , or $\mathcal{O}(A_i)$, there are some assumptions which can be made. If this was an agent based model running on patches, where an agent queries the 4 or 8 cardinal directions for proximity, then $\mathcal{O}(A_i)$ is constant for any N . If A_i involves using a spatial

index to determine proximity, then $\mathcal{O}(A_i) = \log(N)$ for R-tree indexes. “k-nearest neighbour” queries and other proximity, line of sight or graph network queries can be similarly quantified. While each agent’s A_i calculation time can be accelerated with parallel processing, there is memory contention or inter-process communication which will limit acceleration. Agents querying other agents on the same chip is fast, while querying across other compute nodes in the same cabinet is slower and going outside to other cabinets even slower still. These messages get queued for delivery, which causes the non-parallel part of the computation to be proportional to the amount of agent interaction.

The scaling factor between number of agents, N , and percentage parallelisation, p , will determine how suitable a model is for exascale acceleration. Equation 3 might be a more realistic model of how agent communication scales with number of agents than linearly as in the original equation 1. Benchmarks, proxy applications and real world testing are needed to generate data which can be used for prediction.

$$T_{run} = S(N^2 A_i + N A_t) \tag{3}$$

By working backwards, the percentage of the program being speeded up by parallelisation can be estimated and related to the number of agents to see if particular models are suitable for exascale acceleration.

Central to this effort are proxy applications which are designed to be small segments of real world code suitable for optimisation. One obvious improvement that can be made to the agent based modelling program loop is to allow for different time steps to be interleaved for agents that are guaranteed not to interact with each other. This is a classic graph partitioning optimisation scheme. Imagine if there were two islands of agents with no possibility of communication between them. Each can be processed in a separate parallel group, as we know there are no dependencies between them, which increases the level of parallelism possible on the hardware. This type of optimisation scheme was discussed at the roadmap workshop in Glasgow, resulting in the suggestion that maybe agent based modelling at the level of exascale should centre around graph agent based models? This is another performance factor which needs to be determined through real world experimentation.

Finally, batch parallel schemes are an obvious example of pure parallel computation. Sensitivity analysis in stochastic agent based models normally involves running the model multiple times to analyse the distribution of results. Even in deterministic models, multiple model runs might be made in order to do a parameter sweep. Each separate run of the model is inherently parallel, but each model requires all the data and storage required for the whole model run. This is heavyweight parallelism, not the more lightweight parallelism offered by updating agents in parallel where they share the same environment. The amount of data that the model carries with it is going to determine the granularity of

how many batches can be run simultaneously. However, it is important to recognise the potential for parallelism at different levels.

It is important to note here that “in model parallelism” is a requirement for exascale computing. If the model itself does not take advantage of the accelerator hardware, then it cannot ever achieve exascale and should probably be run on a petascale computer instead.

Taking Frontier as an example, it uses 9,472 AMD EPYC Trento 64 Core 2GHz CPUs (606,208 cores) together with 37,888 Radeon Instinct MI250X GPUs (8,335,360 cores). If we assume 100 GFLOPS (or 136 GFLOP?) for the Trento as typical for a CPU and the quoted FP64 peak for an MI250X as 47.9 TFLOP then:

$$\begin{aligned} GPU &: 37888 \times 47.9 \text{ TFLOP} = 1.8 \text{ EFLOP} \\ CPU &: 9472 \times 100 \text{ GFLOP} = 0.000947 \text{ EFLOP} \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Alternatively, for the CPU a max throughput of 16 double precision floating point operations per clock cycle for AVX 2 instructions could be assumed, with a clock of 2GHz to give:

$$CPU : 9472 \times 16 \times 2GHz = 303 \text{ TFLOP} = 0.0003 \text{ EFLOP} \tag{5}$$

This is close to the first figure of 0.000947 EFLOPS, which both mean that, without acceleration on Frontier, you can only be doing petascale computing. The GPU/CPU speed ratio is approximately 1900:1. The ORNL User Manual for Frontier also contains some interesting calculations about theoretical and achievable speeds in “ORNL User guide, Theoretical Roofline” [ORN24].

Up to this point only GPU accelerators have been assumed, but alternative accelerator hardware does exist. The Argonne National Labs ALCF AI Test Bed [Vis22] provides some performance data for the different types. These fall into the categories of GPU, TPU, IPU, LPU and FPGA. The Argonne group tested the following accelerators: Groq (LPU - language processing unit), GraphCore, Bow IPU, Cerberas CS-2, SambaNova Datascale (billion parameter LLMs), Intel Habana. While these were AI tests, this is important because an AI test of a Tensorflow model is still relevant for an agent based model that might use Tensorflow as a library for vector and matrix acceleration. There is significant overlap between the AI world and the ABM world which can be exploited. The inclusion of FPGA here is probably a step too far at this point in time. It has been mentioned by Jack Dongarra as a possible future to go beyond exascale level computing, but the basic idea is to create a dedicated piece of hardware which performs some computation rather than using a general purpose computer. This is currently possible for some simple things like neural networks or mathematical computations, but

a complex piece of software like an agent based model is beyond current technology.

While most of the discussion has been around the acceleration hardware and program optimisation, this is inextricably linked to the power question. The Frontier computer consumes 45 Mega Watts of power. These are not machines that anybody is going to sit in front of and wait for a result from. Graphical user interfaces are not relevant for these machines and a 1 hour run of an agent based model will be expensive just in the amount of electricity it consumes. However, well optimised programs bring the run time down by using resources more efficiently. By reducing the amount of data being moved around in memory, so the power requirements are reduced and the run time is improved. There is a definite financial incentive to write efficient models.

To finish this section, there are some questions left unanswered. What is the reference architecture? Is every exascale computer different? Do we optimise for one architecture, or take a more pragmatic approach with write once, run anywhere? Does the amount of time we could be allocated on an exascale machine justify the time required to make our models run efficiently at that scale? What is the science case for exascale? These are the questions which an exascale scientist/software developer must answer.

5.5 Messaging: Agent Communications and Physical Interconnect

The physical construction of an exascale computer starts with a compute node in a rack. Multiple racks connect together inside a cabinet and cabinets are arranged to form the whole computer. There is a physical network connecting all of the components together in a topology known as a “Dragonfly” network, which was pioneered by Cray [Kim+08]. The agent based model uses an interaction network of agents which is in software, but the hardware imposes physical limits on these interaction speeds. Communicating on chip or on the same node is fastest, followed by node to node communication and lastly cabinet to cabinet. As the dragonfly network is not fully connected, some connections might require multiple hops to get to their destination. The physical layout of dragonfly is a compromise between fully connected, which is too dense to be physically possible, and reducing the number of hops between network devices. On all the exascale machines currently being built, worst case scenario is stated as being three hops across the network. As the number of groups in the system, the number of routers per group and the number of between router channels making up the physical dragonfly network is fixed by the computer’s architecture, this determines how the model scales across the hardware¹². The

¹²See [TWR17] for a diagram of how the parameters affect the topology.

“Message Passing Interface”, or MPI, is one standard used to send messages across this network between agents, but other variants exist. Due to the latency required for communication, this is something to be minimised in agent based models for performance reasons. Network bandwidth on Frontier’s Slingshot network is quoted as 12.8Tbits/sec.

Due to the size and compute power of an exascale machine, it is probable that very few agent based models will be big enough to require communications outside of the local node group. The Frontier computer has 512GB of CPU memory, 4x128GB of GPU memory and 4TB flash memory per node and there are two nodes per rack. One aim of the ExAMPLER systematic Literature review is to discover how big the agent based models in the literature actually are and whether any have the potential for scaling up to this level.

5.6 Batch Parallel or Model Parallel? Sensitivity

The previous section, 5.4, on hardware and acceleration showed that running batch parallel runs of agent based models without acceleration results in only petascale computing. This was a question that has been asked at all of the roadmap workshops to determine if modellers are doing “in model” acceleration, or using regular HPC to accelerate batches of model runs in order to do sensitivity analysis. Monte Carlo simulation is a similar technique where a model is run multiple times with different random seeds to explore the distribution of its behaviour. The Exascale Project’s “MCB” proxy app¹³ for Monte Carlo benchmarks on parallel architectures shows that this has already been explored on exascale architectures. Ensemble weather forecasting is another area that appears similar, with the European “ESCAPE 2”¹⁴ project researching weather and climate prediction at Exascale. The UK Met Office¹⁵ is also a major partner in the UK’s ExCALIBUR programme. Batch parallel agent based models may share some traits with both Monte Carlo algorithms and Ensemble Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP), but it could well transpire that social science agent based models have more complicated characteristics than running physics equations over a global grid, requiring more work to accelerate to exascale. This could be the key selling point of exascale ABMs if the increased power of 10^{18} floating point operations per second led to expanded sensitivity analysis being built into models, giving a new level of confidence to this type of modelling. This was one of the areas that was discussed at the Michigan iEMSs workshop. It is also worth mentioning that this could be a step change of the same magnitude as ensemble modelling was in the 1990s when it was introduced by the UK Met Office and ECMWF. Although the

¹³MCB Proxy App: <https://proxyapps.exascaleproject.org/app/mcb/>

¹⁴ESCAPE 2 webpage: <https://www.hpc-escape2.eu/>

¹⁵UKMO ExALIBUR: <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/approach/collaboration/spf/excalibur>

technique was known for many years before, as Lewis writes in “Roots of Ensemble Forecasting” [Lew05], it required an increase in computing speed before it was feasible. The inclusion of comprehensive sensitivity analysis distributions with agent based models would be a game changing feature. This is a strong science case for exascale agent based modelling.

5.7 Development Environment and Step-up Machines

Few models will be run on a laptop and then ported directly to a £900 million exascale computer. The more likely transition is from regular HPC to accelerated exascale, which favours the scientific disciplines already making extensive use of petascale computing. To jump from laptop or desktop level straight up to exascale is a revolutionary step up. The ORNL’s Frontier computer used “Crusher” as their step up machine for initial testing before building up the full machine one cabinet at a time. The Argonne National Labs “Aurora” computer deployed as a single cabinet for testing applications before being scaled up to the full machine. In the UK, the EPCC deployed GPU accelerators for their ARCHER 2 petascale machine, which researchers could apply to use for testing. All these machines provide steps towards exascale, but are an end point in development rather than being a day to day development environment that ordinary model developers can use. The question is, what hardware and software combinations would allow agent based model developers to build models at small scale, but which allow an easy path towards scaling up to exascale sized models? The computer games industry makes extensive use of GPU programming, so a desktop computer with a high end graphics card would seem to be an obvious choice for a development machine for exascale models. The Artificial Intelligence industry is the other major user of GPU accelerators, with Large Language Models and other neural network applications, which has provided the driving force behind the NVIDIA chips which are now being used to power exascale computing. This is encouraging for two reasons. Firstly, there is expertise in these industries in how to program and optimise for these technologies that can be leveraged for ABM development. Secondly, with this technology slowly filtering down into all forms of computing, there is enough hardware being developed and shipped to consumers for this to no longer be considered a niche area. Google’s TPU (Tensor Processing Unit) neural network chips are shipping in the latest phones for speech recognition, while Apple are following suit with AI accelerators for laptops and Microsoft are offering the Azure Cloud AI platform. If one of the perceived risks of exascale was that it would be controlled by big technology companies, then the proliferation of this technology into everyday use is an indicator that this might not be the case. While only the big AI companies can afford

to develop and train their own large language models, enough of this hardware is around in general use to provide a pathway from a desktop model up to exascale, where a science case can be made for using a Government owned or academic exascale computer. One of the themes that came out of the Michigan iEMSs workshop, where they are already using the US exascale computer, is that software developers who can develop and optimise for these highly parallel platforms are now required. The proliferation of the technology into everyday use can only be good for increasing this skills base.

One final point to be made concerns the science case for exascale and why a model might need to be scaled up. The systematic literature review identified lots of models running at small scale (i.e. laptop), but very few running at the HPC level. If you have a model running perfectly well with 10,000 agents, what is the reason for running it with 10 million agents? Is there expected to be a step change in the results due to the increased size? How can this be justified when writing a business case for using a computer that might cost thousands of pounds per hour? A related question is to ask what it is that needs to be scaled up. In agent based models, this might be increasing the number of agents, increasing the number of interactions between agents, or increasing the complexity of the agent's decision algorithm. Additionally, for spatial models, the size of the study area can be increased, which probably increases the number of agents and interactions as a consequence. As an example, a COVID-19 simulation of Devon might be increased to cover the whole of the UK in order to avoid edge effects at the limits of the model from causing problems. It might be that the science case justification for using exascale in agent based models is to form a closed system? The other justification could be high fidelity models. Either way, some more theoretical work on large scale models would be useful in stepping up to exascale modelling. If the small model and the large model produce different results, then which one is right? Where does the data required to seed a large scale model come from? These were topics of discussion at the iEMSs workshop. The main conclusion from all of this is that there needs to be a progression in development, starting at the small scale where data is readily available and development is easier, transitioning up to exascale models as data and models develop and confidence in models is built up slowly. The "step up" is less of an immediate transition and more a path towards discovery as models adapt. Not all models will make it all the way to exascale though.

5.8 Results: Visual Analytics and Spatial Data

The London Visioning Workshop, run in November 2023, identified the analysis of exascale generated data as being a potential problem. Bigger models can generate bigger data, whether that involves debugging

traces for tracking down problems, generating final reports and graphs for large numbers of agents, or visualising results across a larger spatial scale. The potential for exascale models to generate data beyond what is possible to analyse is a real threat. In this respect, the Michigan iEMSs workshop was extremely helpful as we heard from researchers actually doing this on the already working U.S. Frontier computer. The procedure they described is to run the model on the exascale computer and then move the results files onto a high speed file system local to the exascale computer. This high performance file system allows the use of Jupyter notebooks and all the other usual analytic techniques, but at higher speed and scale. From here, result sets can be scaled down to a level manageable at the desktop level and suitable for wider dissemination. It is interesting to imagine a working pattern where models scale up to exascale to run and then produce data that gets scaled down from exascale back to a manageable level for analysis.

Different levels of debugging are going to be required in models depending on what stage of development they are at. For models being run for the first time at the higher scale, more verbose debugging information is required by the developer as this will be required to verify that the model is performing correctly and help identify any problems. Debugging on an exascale computer via an interactive session is likely to be costly in terms of the number of compute credits used and how much time is involved. If local debugging before moving to exascale is possible, then this is the preferred option. Exascale debugging should be exclusively exascale issues with application software and libraries and not model logic problems. However, bugs have a habit of appearing where you least expect them, so all options need to be covered. Just make sure the model is producing sensible results before turning the compute up and spending money on exascale credits though. This highlights another potential threat from exascale modelling, where it is possible to run out of compute units before completing a project. If the exascale results do not come back as expected, or need further verification runs, then the required compute might exceed the project budget. Agent based modelling may have a potential mitigating factor here, because, if the project plan called for 1000 runs of sensitivity analysis and the development took longer than expected, then a project might get away with 500 runs and still present scientifically meaningful results.

Visualisation of results is not something to be underestimated, though. If the simulation contained 100 million agents, then this is not going to be put on a web page and made interactive for other researchers to explore and verify. The question of “reproducible, open, science” came up repeatedly at the workshops in this respect. Does the fact that a high performance computer has been used to produce the results prevent the experiment from being repeated by other research groups? It certainly limits the repeatability to a few institutions with access to this

type of resource, but this same problem is seen in other disciplines where large scale resources are required. The fact is that the experiment can be repeated with more modest computing resources, only over a longer timescale. Even accepting that the doubling of speed every eighteen months, which was predicted in Moore's Law, is no longer true, computer performance still continues to improve. Today's exascale might still be the next generation's desktop performance, so these large scale models can be seen as the fore runners of experiments that will be tested in the future to an increasing degree. They will succeed or fail and give rise to new theories as the survival of the fittest models over time reveals.

6 Methodology: First Steps to Exascale

Based on the workshops, discussions with researchers and the systematic literature review, the following is a list of recommendations for moving to exascale ABM. These fall into the categories of, performance and how to get it, whether a model is suitable for exascale and what the ABMSS community needs to be doing to build a path from desktop models to petascale and then to exascale.

Recommendation 1: grids, graphs and free moving spatial agents

The first recommendation is that the agent interaction algorithm dictates the degree of parallelism achievable. Small scale tests of models need to be conducted before moving to exascale to determine whether the type of model being run is suitable. If the degree of potential parallelism is too low, then consider petascale instead.

If no agent ever interacted with any other agent, then the simulation could run without any parallel dependencies on other agents and could take full advantage of the massive parallelism offered by the exascale machine. However, in order to be called an agent based model, agents must interact with each other or with their environment. The algorithm that they use to do this is critical to the percentage of parallelisation that can be achieved by the model. It was pointed out earlier that agent based models running on grids and cellular automata make obvious candidates for parallel optimisation. An agent can have 4 or 8 neighbours on a regular grid, which lends itself to a matrix representation and fits the pattern of existing proxy apps for exascale applications which often use 2 or 3 dimensional grids.

Agent based models running on graph networks offer an interesting potential solution for the parallel computing problem. Graph partitions of guaranteed non-interacting agents can be run as parallel simulations. An example of this type of interaction is a virus infecting a human population via a contact network.

Finally, the type of model where agents are free to roam across a

spatial extent presents the most difficult challenge. Agent visibility algorithms might be dependent on the physical environment, for example the pedestrian evacuation of a tube station or sports stadium. It might be that expressing this as a grid based problem allows for a faster simulation, at the expense of reduced spatial resolution, or maybe the answer is a graph representation of space?

Recommendation 2: the path to exascale begins with petascale

Models need to be using the GPU accelerators to benefit from exascale. The systematic literature review identified many models being run at the desktop level, but comparatively few being run on high performance computing architectures. Desktop computers with high end graphics cards can touch 95 teraflops for FP32 or 1.5 petaflops for FP8 calculations, based on the NVIDIA RTX4090 specifications. This level of acceleration is relatively cheap and accessible to researchers now, but is underused according to the systematic literature review that we conducted. New models developed using desktop accelerators make good candidates for moving up to exascale. The FLAME GPU library provides one path into learning this architectural change, as does Agents.jl for the Julia programming language. Programming directly in CUDA, ROC or OpenCL is probably too close to the hardware level and will require too long a development time, but is the path to ultimate performance. The key here is that a model developed and running on a desktop accelerated system can immediately benefit from a step up to a server grade GPU without modification, which will offer higher memory bandwidth for larger scale models.

The path to exascale is a gradual journey of model expansion. Jumping directly from a model running on a researcher’s desktop straight up to exascale is unrealistic. There is also the awkward question of why the model isn’t already making use of petascale HPC? Two jumps in performance is harder to justify than one, so making the case for moving a desktop model straight to exascale is hard to support based on both the science case and the computing case. Expanding the size of the model is likely to require changes to the data it uses as input and to the model itself, as there are likely to be issues flagged with the science behind it. Regular petascale HPC seems like a more obvious route to gradually scale up a model and determine whether it is a candidate for exascale or not. This comes back to the “evolution or revolution” question from earlier. It seems likely that models will evolve from HPC onto exascale, but the computing architecture is more of a revolution. Agent based modelling is more than just vector and matrix maths on grids. Having a smaller petascale CPU model which can be used to verify an expanded exascale GPU model is a useful option to have.

Recommendation 3: making the science case and the “Time to Science” question

Exascale computing is described as extreme scale, while petascale ABMSS has proved to be elusive in the strategic literature review. There are likely to be very few ABMSS applications that can make a science case for running at this level, as tier 1 computing is the top level of UK science and simulation. Looking for evidence of agent based models in the prizes awarded for high performance computing, for example the ACM Gordon Bell Prize¹⁶, has found none. These are the science projects that the ABMSS community is competing against in order to get time on the computer. In order to make a science case for using exascale, a theoretical basis for increasing the model size is required. In the earlier section 1.4 reporting the Glasgow Roadmap Workshop in April 2024, the question about what constitutes *big* in an agent based model was asked. Geographically big can make a good case for exascale in the context of virus propagation (e.g. in the Epstein global model [Eps09]) or global economies. The science driver here could be having a closed system with no edge effects connecting to a world outside the simulation. Simulations with large numbers of agents need the same level of fidelity in their input data, so this type of scaling may turn out to be limited by data availability. This discussion came from the iEMSSs workshop where the U.S. researchers already had a working exascale computer. The idea of “human in the climate loop” modelling was another interesting suggestion for justifying the science case. Climate models are fine as physics models, but do not model the human population’s change in behaviour, which in turn feeds back into the climate model. This type of human-centric modelling could increase the fidelity of existing climate models.

The other recommendation to come out of the iEMSSs workshop is the “time to science” question. Some models are only run once to obtain an answer and are then discarded, while others are run routinely many times over. This dictates how much effort is put into the software development. The time to science includes the software development time required to make the model work, in addition to the actual run time of the model. It might be that it is easier to develop a model for petascale that runs longer than to develop using accelerators at exascale for a modest improvement in run time. This comes back to whether a model is suitable for exascale and whether it is economic to spend researcher money on bespoke model development for a piece software that is only targeting a single computer architecture. The recommendation here is to target the science first, by running possibly inefficient code in the first instance, and then optimise a piece at a time as required.

The conclusion of all this is that the science question rapidly falls apart if the model only achieves petascale speeds when running on exascale. There is a very real cost to research projects in stepping up a

¹⁶ACM Gordon Bell Prize for high performance computing: <https://awards.acm.org/bell>

scale, which may not be fully justified by the science benefits.

Recommendation 4: ABMSS proxy apps are needed

Proxy models enable the modellers to show the research software engineers what they want to make work faster, plus modellers can use existing bits of optimised proxy models where they are relevant. This is a resource of accelerated code that model developers can dip into as needed.

Frameworks are also worth mentioning, as the Python and Tensorflow proxy model pattern shows how AI accelerated ABM could work. Although Tensorflow is intended for AI, the underlying vector and matrix manipulations that it uses are available for any agent based model that can use this type of mathematical acceleration. A lot of effort has been put into the development of certain libraries for AI by big technology companies recently because it is a resource that they use themselves.

Specialised agent based modelling frameworks designed for GPU acceleration, for example FLAME GPU, are useful, but performance at exascale level is still unknown. Again, a proxy app using a GPU ABM framework would be extremely useful for performance testing. It would also advertise to potential model developers the amount of time and effort that would be required to take their own science case to exascale. Co-design of this type is useful because research software engineers can make improvements to the proxy code that will then filter down into science models. Increasingly, it is looking like exascale ABMSS is not a single person activity, but more of a project team effort. This takes it out of the realm of one person on a laptop making a model, which is the case that frequently appears in the systematic literature review.

Many of the models described in the literature review were Netlogo based. This creates a problem, because running a Java Virtual Machine and Java (or Scala) on exascale is likely to be inefficient. A proxy app to test this hypothesis would be extremely useful and answer the question of whether model developers should try scaling their Netlogo models like this to get them running with minimal changes, or whether bespoke models and frameworks are necessary.

Finally, proxy apps would provide bits of reusable code, which could create a snowball effect for modellers wanting to use exascale. The more accelerated models are out there, the lower the bar to entry.

Recommendation 5: emulator models and surrogates for policy

At the London Visioning Workshop in November 2023, the idea of using the exascale computer to optimise an agent based model so that it could be run on a smaller computer was first suggested. This is a potentially very good use case for a model that is run once on exascale to optimise and then run many times on the desktop to get the maximum payback for the initial investment in exascale time. Gaussian process models were discussed at the meeting with the Exeter mathematics group and

then again at the Glasgow roadmap workshop in April 2024. The basic idea is to use the exascale computer's power to search the output space of the agent based model in order to build a predictor. This is a technique which requires further research to determine its viability and to put bounds on what can and cannot be predicted. The question of whether Gaussian Process Models can show emergent behaviours is a valid question which was discussed at the Glasgow workshop. There are some papers starting to appear on this subject, for example [MM24], but it is still an active area of research.

The use case explored in the workshops was for policy applications of ABMSS, where an emulator model circumvents the bureaucracy and time necessary to get a model running on an exascale computer. It gives an immediacy to the modelling and an interactivity which the exascale computer lacks. This appears to be the most attractive route to achieving the goal of running a one day workshop with policy experts where they have the opportunity to run lots of simulations in real time, not having models taking hours to run, and use this to explore real policy issues in the same room.

7 Conclusions

Exascale may seem expensive at first, but it has the potential to save money in the short to medium term. As Archer 2 is currently running to capacity, there is an established need for high performance computing. The Frontier and Aurora computers have topped the Green 500 list, showing that scales of economies exist in their petaflops per watt energy figures. Overall, for the amount of science currently being done at supercomputer level in the UK, an exascale machine could be more efficient. This will become apparent when figures for the U.S. exascale computers are published. In addition to this, the justification for exascale could be a financial one rather than a science one. Given a disaster event like a flood, extreme weather or a pandemic, having a national exascale computer to do modelling and prediction could save lives and money. Having to use a European or U.S. computer in a real-time emergency is going to cause a delay in response. In addition to this, the exascale computer can be used for forward modelling, for example large scale infrastructure proposals, new airports, new towns and large scale house building and urban modelling. There is a clear financial case to be made for an exascale asset that will save money in the long run through improved modelling and planning for UK developments.

If agent based modelling and social simulation is to make use of exascale, then there is a need for proxy apps, which form the building blocks that new exascale models and frameworks can be built on. These need to be social simulation examples as distinct from the physics, materials and climate examples which exist at present. Example models of

real world social simulation systems are also required as exemplars to show what exascale can do that petascale could not. There is a science case to be made for modelling at this level, whether this means big geographically, big economically, or through large scale agent interaction or compute intensive agents. The 2008 paper by North and Macal at the Argonne National Labs [Nor+08] goes some way towards real world cases of extreme scale modelling, but more up to date research is needed.

In order to move agent based social simulation models up the performance scale, a step up machine and suitable development environment are required. Guidance in the form of a best practices document for agent based modellers would lower the bar to entry. A GPU equipped desktop computer would seem to be a good starting point for developing a model which targets exascale acceleration. There do not appear to be any examples in the literature review which can provide real world experience at this point in time.

Exascale computing is extreme computing and relies on acceleration to achieve its speed. It was shown earlier that an application that does not specifically target the accelerators can only achieve petascale speeds. The key is how to demonstrate that model code is exascale ready and will benefit significantly from the higher performance parallel computing? Batch parallel won't work without in-model acceleration and can only achieve petascale computing. However, the use of the massive parallelism of the exascale computer to do sensitivity analysis is identified as a key benefit for exascale agent based social simulation.

In conclusion, while exascale computing is still an emerging and developing technology, the key driving factor is that high performance computing leads to high performance science

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